

EVOLVE2CARE

D5.2 – Interim Reports

WP5 – Project Coordination and
Management

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List of Abbreviations

KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
LL	Living Lab
Mx	Month x
WP	Work Package
ExAB	External Advisory Board
EAB	Ethics Advisory Board
EDIH	European Digital Innovation Hubs Network
KICs	Knowledge and Innovation Communities
EIT	European Institute of Innovation and Technology
EHTEL	European Health Telematics Association

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Executive Summary

This Interim Report provides a comprehensive overview of the activities carried out during the first six months (M1–M6) of the EVOLVE2CARE project. The project is structured into three main phases: (1) stakeholder and needs analysis, (2) development of the Accelup marketplace and experimentation framework, and (3) implementation of Living Lab-based experimentation services for HealthTech innovation in transitional care.

During this initial reporting period, the primary focus was on **Phase 1**, implemented through **Work Package 1 (WP1)**. Key achievements include the development of a protocol for identifying barriers and enablers to innovation in transitional care, followed by extensive stakeholder engagement through surveys and interviews involving 75 participants from 33 countries. Insights were synthesized into two deliverables: **D1.1**, which highlights innovation barriers and drivers, and **D1.2**, which presents a validated KPI framework. This framework addresses both collaboration dynamics between Living Labs and innovators, and the implementation potential of HealthTech solutions. Two repositories were developed to guide evaluation and impact assessment efforts.

Preparatory actions for **Phase 2** were also initiated under **Work Package 2 (WP2)**. These included the drafting of Open Call documentation, and the design of two online training programs targeting Living Lab operators and innovators/researchers. Training topics will cover stakeholder engagement, regulatory frameworks, co-creation, and innovation strategies, with sessions scheduled between May and November 2025.

Cross-cutting activities were conducted under **WP4 (Communication, Dissemination and Outreach)** and **WP5 (Project Coordination and Management)**. WP4 successfully developed the project's visual identity, website, templates, and targeted communication campaigns. WP5 focused on ensuring effective governance and coordination, including the establishment of the External Advisory Board and the Ethics Advisory Board. Three key deliverables (D5.1, D5.2, and D5.3) were submitted, addressing internal processes, interim project reporting, and innovation/IPR management respectively.

Overall, the EVOLVE2CARE project has laid a solid foundation for its future phases by achieving key milestones in stakeholder engagement, methodological development, and operational planning.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Project Overview

EVOLVE2CARE focuses on HealthTech experimentation practices to standardise and enhance the collaboration between Living Labs and innovators in the context of the Transitional Care sector. Challenges ranging from aging populations to complexity of medical conditions and regulatory frameworks bring a growing recognition of the importance of experimentation practises. By subjecting innovations to real-world environments that involve end-users and stakeholders, EVOLVE2CARE provides innovators with access to services for testing and validating research and products.

The project focuses on three Use Cases (UC): i) Hospital discharge management; ii) Homecare monitoring solutions; and iii) Aging population & care transitions, engaging stakeholders across the whole value chain to examine complexities, barriers and enablers that regulatory framework poses to the development and commercialisation of healthcare innovations.

1.2. WP5 Description

The primary aim of WP5, led by AUTH, is to guarantee the successful implementation of the project. Its specific objectives include:

- Overseeing and managing the overall execution of the project.
- Ensuring adherence to the legal, contractual, financial, and reporting obligations outlined by Horizon Europe and the European Commission.
- Delivering the project on schedule and within budget while promoting effective communication between participants and work packages (WPs) and maintaining correspondence with the European Commission.
- Addressing technical, intellectual property rights (IPR), innovation management, and compliance with the data management plan.

1.3. Purpose and scope of the deliverable

This document outlines the activities carried out during the first six months (M1–M6) of the EVOLVE2CARE project. It details the progress made toward achieving the project's objectives and provides the current status of the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). Updates are organized by Work Package (WP) and Task.

1.4. Structure

D5.2 “Interim Reports” includes 8 sections that cover the following areas:

- **Section 1 Introduction:** A brief description of the document’s purpose and structure.
- **Section 2 Project progress overview:** Provide a summary of the overall project progress for this reporting period (M1-M6) and the progress towards realization of objectives.
- **Section 3 Key Performance Indicators:** Presents the current status of KPIs on M6 and the activities towards achievement.
- **Section 4 Explanation of the work carried out per Work Package:** Presents more details on specific tasks and the realization of objectives per WP.
- **Section 5 Project Impact and policy recommendations:** this section describes the impact produced by the project for this first period and how this can be applied to Policy recommendations.
- **Section 6 Conclusions:** The conclusions drawn from this first period of operations.

2. Project progress overview

EVOLVE2CARE activities are organized in three Phases:

- **Phase 1** is dedicated to identifying and defining the specific needs and requirements of the key stakeholders involved in—or affected by—the validation of HealthTech solutions within the transitional care sector. This phase is primarily carried out under **Work Package 1 (WP1)**.
- **Phase 2** focuses on developing the Accelup marketplace’s core modules and services, as outlined in Task 1.4. These components are essential for enabling the functionality of the **EVOLVE2CARE experimentation space**, particularly for facilitating the connection between innovators and researchers in transitional care and supporting their use of Living Lab services available through the marketplace. This work is mainly conducted under **Work Package 2 (WP2)**.
- **Phase 3** involves the actual implementation of experimentation services. During this stage, HealthTech innovations relevant to transitional care will be tested within the Living Lab infrastructures identified in the previous phase. This phase is primarily executed under **Work Package 3 (WP3)**.

This deliverable outlines the activities carried out during the first six (6) months of the project (M1–M6), with a primary focus on **Work Package 1 (WP1)**. The objective during this period was to gain a comprehensive understanding of the stakeholders within the HealthTech innovation ecosystem in transitional care, explore the challenges they face, and identify their specific needs.

The work began with the development of a protocol for identifying barriers and drivers to innovation (Task 1.1), which was presented and discussed during the Kick-off Meeting held in Thessaloniki. This was followed by a **stakeholder mapping workshop**, where stakeholders in the transitional care domain were grouped into six (6) main categories. Each partner was assigned responsibility for engaging specific stakeholder groups, while project-wide dissemination activities were also planned to ensure broad visibility of the work.

The study began with a literature review, followed by the distribution of an online questionnaire. Respondents were also invited to express their willingness to participate in a follow-up interview. A total of **75 participants** completed the questionnaire, representing **33 countries** (17 EU, 4 Associated, and 12 non-EU countries). Subsequently, **32 interviews** were conducted with participants from 10 different countries. The data collected were analyzed and synthesized into a set of **key drivers** and **key barriers** to innovation in the transitional care sector. The results are reported in D1.1 submitted in M4.

Building on the identified barriers and enablers, the second part of the work focused on identifying and analyzing the needs of key stakeholders—researchers, Living Lab operators, end-users, and regulators—and translating these into a practical **KPI framework**. The analysis centered on two core dimensions: (1) the collaboration between Living Labs and innovators, and (2) the implementation of HealthTech solutions in transitional care.

As a result, two distinct KPI repositories were developed:

- The **Use Case Evaluation KPI Repository**, addressing individual collaborations and end-user engagement.
- The **Impact Assessment KPI Repository**, focusing on broader aspects such as regulatory readiness, financial sustainability, and social inclusion.

To ensure practical relevance, the framework was refined through a stakeholder-driven validation process. **Internal feedback** was gathered via an online workshop with project partners, while **external validation** involved **three thematic webinars** with experts from healthcare, regulation, innovation, and Living Labs. Further insights were collected during a live session at the 14th Medical Conference of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki and through collaboration with the GILL project, particularly to enhance KPIs related to gender-responsive and inclusive innovation. The final KPI framework is presented in D1.2 (M6).

In parallel, the consortium initiated preparations for Phase 2 (WP2), focusing specifically on organizing the material and processes for the upcoming Open Calls. Sploro, as the leader of Task 2.2, took the lead in drafting the Open Call documentation, with all partners contributing based on their respective areas of expertise. To ensure alignment and coherence across the consortium, a series of online meetings were held to coordinate efforts, define roles, and streamline the overall process.

Significant planning and conceptualization work has been carried out for both training programs targeting Living Labs (T2.3) and innovators/researchers (T2.4). The structure, content, and delivery timelines have been defined, with sessions scheduled between May and November 2025. Topics span from stakeholder engagement and regulatory frameworks to innovation strategies and co-creation in Living Labs. Training materials are under development, and coordination between ENoLL and AV ensures alignment and complementarity. Both programs will be delivered online, freely accessible, and widely promoted across partner and external networks.

Cross-cutting activities were also carried out to support the project's outreach and visibility (WP4), as well as overall management and coordination (WP5).

Under WP4, key communication assets were developed, including the project logo, website, and social media channels. Standardized templates for presentations, deliverables, meeting agendas, and other project documents were also created to ensure consistency. WP4 further supported participant engagement for Tasks 1.1 and 1.2 through targeted communication materials and dedicated online posts. Additionally, dissemination materials were produced to support partners' participation in external events and conferences, enhancing the project's visibility and stakeholder reach. The Dissemination, Communication and Outreach Strategy and Materials deliverable was submitted on M3.

WP5 was responsible for the overall management and coordination of the project. Deliverable D5.1 was submitted in M4, outlining the procedures for internal communication, meeting organization, reporting, dissemination, and KPI monitoring. As part of WP5 activities, the consortium successfully established both the External Advisory Board and the Ethics Advisory Board. An Ethics Expert was also appointed to review the shortlisted projects from the Open Call. Additionally, Deliverable D5.3 on Technical, IPR, and Innovation Management was developed and submitted in M4, providing a framework for managing innovation assets and intellectual property within the project.

2.1. Objectives

KO#1. Foster user-centric research and support technology upscaling

Progress towards Objective: During the first six months of the EVOLVE2CARE project (M1–M6), important steps were taken to lay the foundation for the harmonization of Living Lab (LL) experimentation services and the creation of a future marketplace supporting HealthTech innovation—particularly in the transitional care sector.

EVOLVE2CARE was presented during the ENoLL Harmonization Working Group meeting, where synergies with ongoing activities were identified and discussed. A key outcome of the meeting was the initiation of a collaborative effort to co-design a standardized application process for external innovators and researchers seeking access to LL services. This process aims to ensure consistency, transparency, and ease of access across different LLs involved in experimentation. As part of this effort, a **co-designed access application template** is under development. This template outlines the core information LLs require from external applicants, helping to streamline onboarding and align expectations between innovators and Living Lab teams. This will feed the activities of T3.1 and T3.2.

The working group brought together representatives from five Living Labs across Europe (including Finland, Belgium, and Switzerland), as well as one from Canada, reflecting a strong international commitment to this harmonization effort. These early activities contribute directly to EVOLVE2CARE's broader goal of promoting standardized LL services, accelerating innovation uptake, and reducing barriers for HealthTech developers entering real-life testing environments.

KO#2. Enable deployment and commercialization

Progress towards Objective: In the first six months (M1–M6), EVOLVE2CARE made strong progress in identifying barriers to HealthTech innovation in transitional care. Through literature review, a stakeholder mapping workshop, a pan-European survey (75 responses from 33 countries), and 32 interviews, the consortium captured key legal, regulatory, financial, operational, and technological challenges.

Building on these insights, two KPI repositories were developed to assess both individual collaborations and broader impact dimensions. These were refined through internal workshops, external webinars, and expert feedback, including sessions at the Aristotle University Medical Conference and input from the GILL project. These activities lay the foundation for upcoming testing of at least 10 innovations and support future dissemination and exploitation efforts.

KO#3. Demonstrate pan-European testing by fostering coordination and regulatory action

Progress towards Objective: While the technical development and enhancement of the Accelup platform (T1.3 and T2.1) are scheduled to begin in the upcoming project phase, EVOLVE2CARE has focused on preparatory activities for the open calls. This includes coordination among partners, drafting of application materials, and alignment of procedures, led by Sploro with contributions from the consortium. These efforts lay the groundwork for launching the matchmaking process between innovators and Living Labs through the Accelup platform.

KO#4. Encourage knowledge sharing and Collaborations

Progress towards Objective: Progress toward this objective will mainly take place in the upcoming phases of the project, particularly as the Accelup platform becomes more advanced and its collaborative features are implemented. Key activities supporting this goal are planned under Task T4.3 – Clustering with EIT KICs, which starts in Month 12 (M12). This task will drive engagement with relevant EU initiatives and support systematic knowledge exchange, coordination, and best practice sharing.

3. Key Performance Indicators

KPI #	Description	Target	Current Status	Steps towards achievement	Responsible Partner
1.1	Training Programs increasing knowledge on experimentation frameworks	2	T2.4: In development. Also, Anthology Ventures and ENoLL have been working closely together to plan and coordinate the training programs (T2.4 and T2.3)	Finalise structure; confirm speakers; deliver webinars; post to platforms	ENoLL/AV
1.2	Living Labs participating in trainings	20	Trainings not started yet	Finalise concept and training program; develop training materials, deliver trainings; design training booklet; create online trainings (MOOC) on the ENoLL Living Labbers Academy. The target audience for the trainings is both ENoLL certified Living Labs (standing at 173) and Living Labs that aim to become certified Living Labs. The invitation for the training series will be shared directly with the ENoLL certified Living Labs using the internal newsletter and communication channels, as well as targeted invitations will be shared with the members of the ENoLL Health &	ENoLL

				Wellbeing Working Group (119 active members). Additionally, the invitation will be shared on ENoLL's and E2C's social media channels.	
1.3	Living Labs engaged in user centric knowledge and experimentation activities	40	<p>Ongoing - 18 participants involved</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 4 ENoLL certified Living Labs have been actively involved in the interview phase to share insights and experiences relevant to the project, within the framework of WP1 – Task 1.1 - 14 Living Labs participants involved in the online workshop series within the framework of WP1 – Task 1.2 	Engagement will continue mainly within the framework of WP1	ENoLL
1.4	Services for testing innovations	10	The list of LL services offering has been developed and validated by ENoLL Harmonization Working Group (WG). EVOLVE2CARE will adopt the outcomes of the WG.	The services that will be tested will be chosen by the Innovators that will participate in the Open Calls.	ENoLL/Harmonization WG
1.5	Action Plans	1	Not started yet	EVOLVE2CARE is in close collaboration with ENoLL Harmonization WG in order to map the services and infrastructures used in transitional care.	AUTH

2.1	Innovations tested	10	<p>Under Task 2.2, we plan to engage 10 or more Living Labs to provide services aimed at testing innovative solutions. These services will support technology upscaling, cost reduction, acceleration of time-to-market, and mitigation of investment risks. The target beneficiaries of these services are Innovators participating in the project.</p> <p>This task is currently in progress, as the Open Call has only recently been launched.</p>	<p>To ensure that 10 innovations are tested, we have established a single Open Call, which has already been launched through two platforms. The first platform, Accelup, is used for matchmaking between Living Labs and Innovators. The second platform is Sploro's Platform, which supports the evaluation, selection, and awarding processes for the matched teams.</p> <p>Our goal is to reach 10 tested innovations by promoting the Open Call through social media channels and active participation in relevant events. This step is currently in progress.</p>	Sploro/AUTH
2.2	Countries covered	20	<p>For Task 2.2, we launched the Open Call on March 17, 2025. Regarding the outreach process, we sent the information via email to over 460 contacts from more than 20 countries. By the time of the first cutoff on May 26, 2025, we will be able to assess whether the minimum</p>	<p>During events like the EIC Summit 2025 and Mobile World Congress - 4YFN, we continued the outreach efforts by promoting the Open Call through SPLORO's official communication channels, as well as through direct contacts from all</p>	Sploro

			number of KPIs has been achieved. This will inform the next steps for the second and third cutoff dates.	partners (e.g., through LinkedIn). This step is currently in progress.	
2.3	Organizations to inform	20	We informed over 20 organisations through email campaigns, targeted outreach, communication channels, direct LinkedIn contact, and events that SPLORO was involved in.	We will continue these outreach activities to achieve the targeted KPI. This step is currently in progress.	Sploro
2.4	Stakeholders researched	>50	During the survey phase, as part of D1.1, we researched 75 stakeholders across all the target groups. A total of 105 participants registered for the online workshop series and one in person session that informed the needs analysis, as part of D1.2	EVOLVE2CARE will continue engaging and research stakeholders in the transitional care ecosystem to inform the activities of T1.3.	Sploro/VILABS
3.1	Supervisory authorities reached	5	The outreach activities of the first stage of the project have already managed to promote the project in several networking events at the European level. For example, the project's dissemination at Mobile World Congress 2025 to several pan-European and international bodies and initiatives of oversight-type, like the European Connected Health Alliance, European Institute of Innovation and	Moving towards the next stages of the dissemination and communication strategy of the project more intensive engagement with supervisory bodies will be sought. Promotion of the project's Open Call and its outcomes will be targeted towards such stakeholders and participation of their representatives in	VILABS

			Technology, GSMA Ministerial Programme and more.	project's forthcoming events will be opted to demonstrate a cross-sectoral paradigm of collaboration and opportunities for regulatory enhancements	
3.2	Countries covered	20	Dissemination and communication activities have already been performed in countries represented within the project, like Greece and Spain. Partners have already documented project dissemination in Pan-European events (e.g. EIC Summit 2025, MWC 2025), local and regional events (e.g. COHEHRE Conference 2025, 14th Annual Scientific Conference of AUTH School of Medicine) and cross-projects' events like the GILL project webinar and ENoLL Harmonization WG that has also reported global representation like Switzerland and Canada	The next stages of the project's dissemination and communication strategy; especially the third one, will elaborate on a roadmap for sustainability of the project's paradigm across Europe and even foster further uptake globally.	VILABS
3.3	Areas identified	3 Uses Cases	First stakeholders' needs analysis has been performed and reported in D1.2.	Based on needs analysis results and mapping of HealthTech ecosystem in transitional care, we will update the Use Case description.	AUTH

3.4	Experimentation spaces: Centralized (Accelup) covering multiple experimentation spaces i.e., LLs	1	Accelup is already running to support the matchmaking of Living Labs and innovators.	New features for Accelup will be specified through the analysis in T1.3.	AUTH/ENoLL
3.5	Regulators reached	10	We have contacted all 7 Regional Health Authorities of Greece in the context of the T1.1 Survey, out of whom 2 have responded providing input and insights	Even though, not all Regional Health Authorities took part in the T1.1 Survey, we have encountered positive responses and interest for future contributions from stakeholders who have agreed to become part of the project's community. Leveraging this foundation of regulatory bodies representation the project will seek to engage with such target groups in the rest of the consortium members' countries and at EU level.	VILABS/AV
4.1	KICs/projects/ EU initiatives reached	7	Currently connections have been established with: - SmartHEALTH European Digital Innovation Hub (EDIH) through the participation of Dimitrios Katehakis in the External Advisory Board (ExAB) - the European Health Telematics Association (EHTEL) through	The consortium works towards establishing connections with other initiatives like EIT. This work will be intensified in Task 4.3 when we will have the first experimentation results.	AUTH/ENoLL

			dedicated calls with the coordination team - GiLL project in the development of KPIs framework (D1.2)		
4.2	Living Labs reached	100	Ongoing Currently 18 Living Lab representatives involved in WP1 – T1.1 and T1.2	All 172 Living Labs within the ENoLL network have been contacted and invited to attend core activities such as the symposium, E2C workshops, and the Open Living Lab Days (OLL). Among them, approximately 80 are active or show a strong interest in health-related topics, in addition to other members involved in the Health Working Group.	ENoLL
4.3	Multipliers reached	20	4 multipliers already reached: - Connections with KIC in Mobile World Congress (MWC2025) - EIT Health Spain through Basque Health Cluster (Maika Sabido in the ExAB) - EHTEL agreed to shared EVOLVE2CARE Open Calls - EVOLVE2CARE is mentioned in SymbIASIS project (funded by EIT Health) as an initiative that can	The EVOLVE2CARE consortium has created a plan of participation in relevant events as well as one to one contacts for establishing connections with EIT KICs. We will also investigate synergies with EDIHs that work on Health and Medicine.	AUTH

			support HealthTech SMEs		
4.4	RTOs reached	20	The dissemination and communication activities have already managed to engage in varying levels with stakeholders from research communities and academia. The concurrent count for such target groups surpasses the 15	Dissemination activities that will showcase the project's outputs, best practises and key insights, spanning from webinars to training materials, and white papers are foreseen for the upcoming stages of the project	VILABS/AUTH
4.5	Knowledge sharing workshops	2	We have already held a series of 3 online workshops titled <u>'Accelerating Innovation in Transitional Care – Identifying Key Needs & Meaningful Impact'</u> in the context of T1.2. The project has synergised with HorizonEU project, GILL, to contribute to its webinar jointly elaborating on integrating social and gender dimensions into the KPIs co-creation.	Additional workshops are foreseen both in digital and hybrid format to disseminate project's significant progresses during key moments	VILABS

4. Explanation of the Work carried out per Work Package

4.1. WP1 – EVOLVE2CARE experimentation space framework

WP progress: WP1 is focused on laying the groundwork for the EVOLVE2CARE experimentation space, identifying the core components needed to foster innovation in transitional care. This includes defining the legal, regulatory, fiscal, technical, operational and socio-economic prerequisites for supporting innovators. The work performed so far has set a solid foundation for the project's future phases, by identifying the key barriers and facilitators faced to introducing HealthTech innovations in the transitional care domain and establishing a comprehensive needs analysis and KPI Framework.

Deliverables Submitted (M1-M6)

D1.1 – Roadmap on navigating the complexities of enabling innovative technologies in transitional care

This deliverable outlines the key findings gathered through literature reviews, surveys, and interviews across a diverse range of stakeholders in the HealthTech ecosystem. The results directly inform the design and implementation of the Open Call and future matchmaking activities.

D1.2 - Stakeholder Needs Analysis and KPI framework

This deliverable presents the first version of the EVOLVE2CARE KPI framework that is based on barriers and drivers identified in D1.1 and complemented by the need analysis performed in T1.2.

4.1.1. Task 1.1 Drivers and Barriers for the development of innovations

This task is part of WP1, and the output of this task was reported under Deliverable 1.1 in January 2025.

The objective of Task 1.1 was to identify and categorise the key enablers and obstacles affecting innovation within transitional care pathways across Europe. To achieve this, a structured and multi-layered methodology was implemented.

The task began with a comprehensive literature review to establish a conceptual framework and align terminology across the consortium. Based on this groundwork, a stakeholder mapping exercise was conducted to identify relevant actors within the HealthTech ecosystem, such as Innovators (researchers, SMEs, startups, corporates), Accelerators / Investors, Living Labs, End-users (Transitional care units, hospitals, practitioners, individuals), Policy makers / Regulatory bodies and EU initiatives (i.e. EIT Health projects)

From this mapping, tailored survey instruments and interview guides were developed to capture perspectives from this broad set of stakeholders. The survey was disseminated through the consortium's communication channels, project partners' networks, and targeted outreach efforts, which led to over 50 valid stakeholder responses. Semi-structured interviews were also conducted with selected stakeholders to gain deeper qualitative insights and validate survey findings.

All data collected was analysed and organised across five domains—legal/regulatory, fiscal, technical, operational, and socio-economic. The resulting findings directly informed the development of Deliverable D1.1 and laid the groundwork for WP2 activities, particularly in shaping the Open Call strategy and identifying suitable Living Labs for testing.

The outcomes of Task 1.1 now serve as a reference for ensuring that the innovation support mechanisms in EVOLVE2CARE are well-targeted and responsive to real-world challenges faced by innovators in the transitional care space.

4.1.2. Task 1.2 Definition of Stakeholders' requirements and KPI framework

During the first semester of EVOLVE2CARE, Task T1.2 successfully identified stakeholder requirements and developed a dual KPI framework to support both use case evaluations and broader impact assessment. Building on the findings of D1.1, stakeholder needs were mapped across two core dimensions: Living Lab–innovator collaboration and HealthTech implementation in transitional care. The resulting **Use Case Evaluation KPI Repository** and **Impact Assessment KPI Repository** were refined through extensive stakeholder engagement, including an internal workshop, three thematic webinars, and a live session at the 14th Medical Conference of AUTH. Input from the GILL project further enriched the framework with gender and inclusivity KPIs. This validated KPI framework will guide the evaluation of the project's activities and will continue to evolve as experimentation progresses.

The next steps involve disseminating the EVOLVE2CARE KPI framework to key stakeholders like EIT Health, to ensure broad adoption and gather feedback. The

framework will be presented to organizations like EHTEL and Era4Health to integrate it into health strategies. The Living Lab and End-User repositories will be shared with Open Call applicants and integrated into the Accelup platform. Continuous feedback and data analysis will help refine the framework and keep it aligned with evolving needs.

4.1.3. Task 1.3 Specification of Use Cases, Marketplace Architecture and Action Plan

As part of Task T1.3, the consortium organized a dedicated session during the project kick-off meeting to discuss and refine the project's Use Cases. In parallel, targeted updates were implemented on the Accelup platform to address the specific requirements of EVOLVE2CARE. Notably, a new section has been designed for the to showcase available funding opportunities, with a CTA 'button' on the landing page (Image 1).

Figure 1 New landing page of Accelup

Clicking the CTA button will lead to a new page that will provide information on the funding topics and the corresponding budget, aiming to enhance the visibility and dissemination of these opportunities to platform visitors. A mock-up of this page is shown below (Image 2).

Figure 2 Funding Opportunity page in Accelup

Since this task relies on input from T1.1 and T1.2, the activities of WP1 were primarily focused on these two tasks until M6. From M6 to M9, activities under T1.3 will be intensified. AUTH has already defined the research plan to support the refinement of the Use Cases. To ensure that the innovators' needs are adequately addressed, we will collect information on existing start-ups and SMEs operating in the HealthTech domain, analyze their Use Cases, and explore how the EVOLVE2CARE Use Cases can be enhanced to cover a wider range of needs. This research will also inform the development of the Action Plan, building on the outcomes of Deliverables D1.1 and D1.2. Furthermore, it will identify key information that should be integrated into the Accelup platform to help address some of the main challenges faced by innovators.

4.2. WP2 – Matching Accelup Experimentation Space and Services with Innovators and Researchers

WP progress: During this reporting period, WP2 activities primarily focused on defining the scouting and selection process for Living Labs, Innovators, and Researchers (Task 2.2), as well as preparing the necessary materials for the launch of the Open Calls.

Significant progress was also made in the development of the training programs for both Living Labs and Innovators. Efforts were concentrated on planning, structuring, and ensuring alignment between the two training programs to create a coherent and complementary learning experience.

Deliverables Submitted (M1-M6)

No deliverables submitted

4.2.1. Task 2.1 EVOLVE2CARE Experimentation Space infrastructure

Not started yet

4.2.2. Task 2.2 LLs, Innovators and Researchers Scouting and selection

This task is primarily related to the Open Call process. The output of this task will be reported in M16 under Deliverable 2.2.

The main activities we have completed so far related to this task are:

- Drafted the **Open Call guidelines**, which include:
 - Call Guidelines, including the management of ties and conflicts of interest
 - Annexes with the application form for both platforms
 - FAQ section for both platforms
 - SME Declaration
 - Partners Review Committee document
- Together with the consortium partners, we established a common approach regarding the criteria, objectives, and expectations for the draft call document.
- We organised brainstorming sessions.
- We drafted and prepared agreements with the selected Living Labs, outlining the terms for opening their facilities to innovators.
- We selected the review committee, made up of representatives from all partner organizations, and drafted the document defining this activity and the evaluation process of the Open Call.
- With the help of AUTH, we contracted the External Ethics expert for the consortium.
- We conducted the scouting process and reached over 460 contacts from the healthcare and HealthTech sectors.
- Partners status meetings
- We established all the activities that will follow in the Open Call process, including actions to be taken after the Open Call closes and after each cut-off period.

Some of the mentioned activities are still in progress (e.g., the scouting process, brainstorming sessions, and partners' weekly status meetings). These activities are organized throughout the entire Open Call period, until October 13, 2025.

4.2.3. Task 2.3 Training Program for Living Labs

Task T2.3 main objective is to design and deliver a program of trainings to support Living Labs in offering their services to innovators in assessing experimental outcomes and commercializing research results. By adopting a structured, service design-based approach, Living Labs will learn how to develop sustainable service offerings, navigate legal and ethical challenges, and enhance stakeholder engagement, thus ensuring a smoother transition from research to market.

Following a thorough conceptualization phase that defined the program's objectives and key themes, six sessions will be delivered on the [ENoLL Living Labbers Academy](#) from (tentatively) May 2025 (M8) to November 2025 (M14). These sessions will be available for free upon registration in the online Academy, and will cover the following key topics:

1. The innovation landscape & role of living labs
2. Creating a procedure or methodology to design the service
3. Ethical, legal & regulatory frameworks
4. Communication & stakeholder engagement
5. Certification & standardisation of Living Labs
6. Measuring impact & evaluating success

Training materials will be developed progressively from April 2025 (M6) to November, aligning with each training session. Additionally, a comprehensive booklet featuring practical tools and resources will be created to support participants both during and after the sessions.

However, as Task T2.3 is still under development, all activities will be fully reported in November 2025 through D2.4.

4.2.4. Task 2.4 Training Program for Innovators and Researchers

This training program envisaged in this task will be reported in M14 (D2.4). It is designed to equip Transitional Care (TC) innovators with essential knowledge and skills to accelerate their innovation journey utilizing Living Labs (LL) infrastructures and services. The curriculum is organized into several key sessions, (initially planned as six modules), each focusing on a critical aspect of the innovation process within the LL context as described in the task. To enhance learning and practical application, each session incorporates a variety of resources, including downloadable PDF guides and toolkits, and visually engaging PPT presentations. Furthermore, the program's

development involves thorough research, benchmarks against existing programs, and incorporates findings from stakeholder research to ensure relevance and effectiveness.

The training program (T2.4) is set to be delivered online, making it accessible to a broad audience. While tentatively scheduled for June to July 2025, the timeline may be adjusted to September 2025 if necessary. AV is currently designing the program as follows; however, it may be subject to changes to accommodate the allocated speakers.

Training Topics:

1. “Design Thinking for TC Innovators - Leveraging LLMs for Faster Innovation”
2. “Business Models for Transitional Care solutions: from Theory to Practice”
3. “IPR Basics for TC Innovators”
4. “Fundraising for TC Innovators”
5. “Utilizing LLMs and No-Code for Iterative Development”
6. “Navigating Ethics, Compliance, and Inclusion in LLMs”

The sessions will feature a range of guest speakers who will provide specialised knowledge for each topic, and interactive content and tools will be deployed to engage the participants in a variety of ways.

Upon completion, participants will be equipped with the knowledge, abilities, and tactics needed to integrate Living Labs into their research and innovation projects successfully. Participants will develop a hands-on understanding of the innovation lifecycle within a Living Lab environment, ultimately fostering the development and implementation of impactful transitional care solutions.

The sessions will be published on social media, as well as through AV, AUTH, Sploro and partner networks, welcoming both experienced innovators and novice researchers who may or may not be familiar with the value provided by utilizing Living Labs as innovation partners.

To ensure complementary content and prevent overlap, AV is collaborating with ENoLL (T2.3 & T2.4). Anyone who would like to participate in the training is welcome to apply (and not limited to those selected in T2.2). Recognizing the importance of widespread dissemination, the training sessions will be recorded and made publicly available on the Accelup platform (and possibly others) for registered users to access at their convenience.

The work is undertaken in close cooperation with ENoLL, who coordinates Task 2.3, with strong alignment and continuity across related initiatives.

4.3. WP3 – Set Up of Accelup experimentation Space and Services Execution, Lessons Learnt and Best practices

No activities – WP have not started yet

4.4. WP4 – EVOLVE2CARE’s People-Centric Experimentation Ecosystem Outreach, Sustainability and Clustering

WP progress: During the first six months of the project (M1–M6), WP4 laid the foundation for EVOLVE2CARE’s dissemination, communication, and outreach strategy with a strong emphasis on awareness raising and stakeholder engagement in view of the project’s Open Calls. A complete visual identity was established, including the logo, a project brand book, and document templates. Key materials such as the project flyer and promotional video were developed and disseminated across channels. The project website was launched in M1, complemented by active social media presence. Partners participated in high-impact physical and online events, including a three-part workshop series targeting innovators and end-users. Stakeholder reach was continuously monitored through a shared reporting tool, ensuring alignment with the KPI framework and setting a strong baseline for the next phases.

Deliverables Submitted (M1-M6)

D4.1 - Dissemination, Communication and Outreach Strategy and Materials

D4.1 defines the project’s dissemination, communication, and outreach strategy, coordinated by VILABS under WP4. Its goal is to raise awareness, engage stakeholders, and support the uptake of EVOLVE2CARE results in transitional care and HealthTech. The strategy was co-developed through a brainstorming session at the Kick-off Meeting and a partner-wide outreach capacity survey. Based on the “7Ws approach” (why, what, who, how, when, where, to whom), it targets key groups—innovators, Living Labs, end-users, policymakers, and EU initiatives—with tailored messaging. A visual identity, website, social media channels, and materials (flyer, templates, video) were delivered in M1–M3 to support early visibility.

Activities are planned across three phases: awareness (M1–M6), community outreach (M7–M14), and sustainability (M15–M24). Initial efforts included launching online

channels, developing materials, participating in events, and stakeholder mapping. Partners began using a shared reporting form to log activities and outreach impact.

KPIs track engagement via website traffic, social media, and events. Coordination is ensured through WP4 meetings, supporting alignment and strategic communication throughout the project.

4.4.1. Task 4.1 EVOLVE2CARE Dissemination, Communication and Outreach for the Open Calls

In summary, key point of the task’s progress are listed below:

Visual Identity: The project’s logo was created right at the project’s start in October 2024 (M1) (see Figure 1). It is designed to represent the concepts of care, innovation and continuity.

Figure 3 EVOLVE2CARE logo

Along with the logo, the project’s **Brand Book** was prepared and share with all the partners to communicate comprehensive guidelines about the project’s visual identity and its properties.

Materials: Drawing from the project logo and colour scheme, a set of templates was delivered, consisting of text documents and presentation templates that entail important instructions for project partners regarding the correct use of the project’s visual features and guidelines for adequate acknowledgement of EU funding. These templates are meant to be used for deliverables, presentations, and external communications of the project. What is more, a meetings background was created to cover the project’s needs in terms of online events.

In addition to the project’s templates, preliminary materials for online and print use were drafted by VILABS and contributions from all partners. Within the timeframe of the current report, several key materials have been made:

- Project’s preliminary promotional slides
- First version of the project’s flyer

- First version of project's business card, featuring information about the Open Call
- Social media cards for digital use (see Online Channels)
- Promotional materials for WP1 activities that required stakeholders' engagement
 - Digital banner and participants' briefings to complement Open Surveys conducted within Task 1.1

Figure 4 Task 1.1 survey example promo materials

- Digital cards, banners and participants briefing to complement the online workshop series within Task 1.2

Figure 5 Task 1.2 workshops example card

Online Channels: The project’s website has been officially launched upon the project’s start in October 2024 (M1), under the domain name <https://evolve2care.eu/>. The major function of the website is to share the project’s progress and outcomes with all the target stakeholders and general audiences. It features the necessary information regarding the project, news about the project, materials and resources. During the first semester of its lifespan, the website has documented 1400 thousand visitors, with nearly 5500 thousand pageviews. The average session time within the reported timeframe is estimated at 1 minute and 25 seconds.

The project’s social media pages were set up in October 2024 (M1) as well. Popular platforms have been selected since such channels play an essential role for sharing messages and communicating with target audiences in almost real time. The project’s strategy has opted to utilise [Facebook](#) and [LinkedIn](#) platforms. VIL is managing the accounts drawing content from project’s website news, events and outreach activities of project partners, significant project developments and news relevant to the project’s scope; while all partners have been providing content and sharing the project’s copies in steady basis. The aggregate table below provides an overview of the con-current social media statistics:

Table 1 EVOLVE2CARE Social Media key insights

Platform	Current Followers	Posts	Reach	Reactions	Impressions
Facebook	43	37	2.5 K	300	n/a
LinkedIn	133	37	n/a	410	9 K

Significant effort has been being put in creating visually engaging and platform-specific content, like social media cards that prompt users to interact with the information about key aspects of the project.

Figure 6 EVOLVE2CARE Social Media cards and posters

YouTube Channel: The YouTube channel was also created in October 2024 (M1). The set up followed the above-described procedures for social media pages. It is named [EVOLVE2CARE Project HorizonEU](#) and is going to feature all the audiovisual materials to be drafted in the context of the dissemination, communication and outreach activities for the project. In fact, the preliminary [animated video](#) of the project was created by VIL in December 2024 (M3) and uploaded to the YouTube channel, while the recorded sessions of the three afore-described online workshops have been made public in a dedicated [YouTube playlist](#).

Newsletter: The Mailchimp account for project’s newsletter was set up in January 2025 (M4), while the project’s website features a sing-up form in both ‘Contact’ and ‘Open Call’ pages as a call-to-action towards the interested users to join the project’s community and keep up with the latest developments. The first project issue was prepared for publication during March 2025 (M6) in order to cover the initiation period of the first project semester.

Networking Activities: Project partners have sought to represent EVOLVE2CARE at external virtual and physical events either as invited speakers or facilitators. These efforts aimed to raise awareness of the project, engage target stakeholders, and support the promotion of the upcoming Open Calls. Below is a list of relevant activities carried out during M1–M6:

- Participation to COEHRE 2024 Conference in Ghent on November 23, 2024, **by AUTH and ENoLL**
- Presentation of the project during the online meeting of ENoLL’s Harmonization Working Group on February 14, 2025, **by AUTH**
- Participation to European Innovation Council (EIC) Summit 2025 in Brussels, Belgium on April 2-3, 2025, **by SPLORO**
- Participation to Mobile World Congress (MWC2025) in Barcelona, Spain on March 3-6, 2025, **by SPLORO and AV**
 - Organisation of panel discussion titled “The Future of Women in Tech: What’s Next?” **by SPLORO, with contributions form AV**
- Organisation of a workshop titled “Innovation in Transitional Care: Unlocking the needs of Healthcare professionals” within the 14th Medical Conference in Aristotle University of Thessaloniki in Thessaloniki, Greece on March 7, 2025, **by AUTH**
- Organisation of an online workshop series titled “Accelerating Innovation in Transitional Care” in March 2025 **by AUTH**
 - First online workshop titled “Empowering Innovators to Transform Transitional Care” on March 4
 - Second online workshop titled “Aligning Innovation with Healthcare Stakeholder Needs” on March 11
 - Third online workshop titled “Regulatory Requirements for Medical Devices in Digital Health” on March 18
- Co-organisation of an online workshop with Horizon Europe project, GILL, on March 29, 2025, **by AUTH and ENoLL**

Publications: During the covered period, emphasis was put on publishing non-peer-reviewed publications in order to foster an initial awareness regarding the project’s scope, fundamental aspects and goals. To this end, blog posts have been curated by VIL, with active consultation from partners as well. By the time this report is conducted, four blogs have been published referring to EVOLVE2CARE core aspects, important findings and how project’s key results can positively impact contemporary challenges of innovation for the Transitional Care. The content of the blogs was sourced in the public deliverables that have already been successfully submitted.

Zenodo Community: The project's [Zenodo community](#) was set up in October 2024 (M1). The platform serves as an open repository where all public deliverables,

presentations, publications, e-newsletters, policy briefs and/or any other document/material that would be useful and interesting for project's stakeholders are uploaded, curated, and made freely available under open access status. By the time of this report, initial communication materials and the project's brand book have been uploaded.

4.4.2. Task 4.2 Exploitation and IPR of Accelup

During the first semester of the project, Task 4.2 paid attention to specific ground-setting issues. In particular, and given the early stage of the project, VILABS consulted with AV, the Task 5.2 leader, to elaborate on the cross-relevant areas of the exploitation and IPR management topics.

To this end, VILABS contributed to the preparation of D5.3 (see below) by addressing (along with main deliverable authors, AV, the concepts of innovations developed in the context of EVOLVE2CARE. The innovations have been categorised as **Internal Innovations**, that is, produced and advanced by the project itself, related to EVOLVE2CARE's KERs (Accelup being a primary KER of the project) and **External Innovations** "Experimentations", that are envisioned to be solutions belonging to researchers that are tested in the Living Labs as chosen through the Open Call.

Setting a clear distinction among the expected KERs and the consequent exploitation and IPR Management modalities has been the focus of Task 4.2 within the period addressed in this deliverable.

4.4.3. Task 4.3 Clustering with EIT KICs

Not started yet

4.5. WP5 – Project Coordination and Management

The activities during this period focused on establishing management processes and communication channels within the consortium. AUTH also prepared detailed guidelines for financial reporting to ensure consistency and compliance.

In parallel, key efforts were dedicated to setting up the Management, Ethics, and Advisory Boards. Additionally, the preparation of the project's first Data Management Plan was a core activity under this Work Package.

Deliverables Submitted (M1-M6)

D5.1 – Project Management Handbook

This Deliverable presents the project management framework for EVOLVE2CARE, outlining all managerial, operational, and data management procedures planned for

the project's duration. It serves as a practical handbook for partners, defining workflows, quality standards, and providing quick-access links for verified project members. Additionally, it includes a comprehensive Data Management Plan (DMP) detailing how project data will be handled, monitored, and protected both during and after the project's completion.

D5.3 - Technical, IPR and Innovation Management

This Deliverable outlines the framework and methodology the Consortium will follow to coordinate technical activities, protect IPR, and manage innovation. It details processes for monitoring technological progress, supporting innovators' ownership of their solutions, and adapting developments to market needs, while also establishing an External Advisory Board.

4.5.1. Task 5.1 Project Coordination and financial management

During this reporting period, AUTH established dedicated communication channels, including mailing lists, a Slack workspace, and a Microsoft Teams channel, to support effective collaboration across the consortium. Bi-weekly stand-up meetings were introduced to closely monitor the project's progress. AUTH also organized and conducted the project kick-off meeting, setting the foundation for the project's implementation. In collaboration with Sploro, AUTH reviewed the "Kronis" platform to support financial management activities. Additionally, AUTH tracked the progress of project KPIs, ensured the timely review and submission of deliverables, and coordinated the planning of the next plenary meeting, which will take place in Istanbul on 12 May 2025.

4.5.2. Task 5.2 Technical, and Innovation Management

T5.2 includes the activities that need to be performed for the technical and innovation management of all the innovations that will be tested/developed during the Living Lab residencies. The methodology of the technical and innovation management has been submitted in D5.3 (M4). D5.3 also included the activities performed for the formation of the External Advisory Board (ExAB), the Ethics Advisory Board (EAB) and the appropriate strategies for the Intellectual Property Rights of the innovations explored during the residencies.

1st activity: External Advisory Board

To ensure quality and impact, the External Advisory Board (ExAB) of EVOLVE2CARE has been selected to offer strategic direction, supporting the project's overarching objectives. Until now there are 4 individuals [[Costas Piliounis](#), [Maika Sabido](#), [Katerina](#)

Zisaki and Dimitrios Katehakis] who will provide a wide range of expertise in areas including Living Labs, Corporate Health Innovation, and Regulatory Matters.

- Costas Piliounis is the Managing Director of PNValue, and a Professor of Management at Rome Business School. He has more than 30 years of management experience in the healthcare industry, specifically diagnostics and pharmaceuticals, previously as Corporate Vice President of NovoNordisk, and Chairman of the Board at BluSense. He is actively involved with the healthtech startups ReTouch (Thessaloniki, GR) and Biocos (Crete) and assists startups and spinoffs as an investor, advisor and consultant.
- Maika Sabido, Project Manager at the Basque Health Cluster, a network partner of EIT Health Spain. Experience in research, development and manufacturing techniques for nano and microelectronic devices, nanostructuring of materials, ISOM., and UPM. Part of the MedLumics team in the development, manufacturing and characterization of a class III medical device with photonic technology. At the Basque Health Cluster she contributes to the growth of the Basque ecosystem of health and biosciences.
- Katerina Zisaki demonstrates a multidisciplinary profile into the Quality and Regulatory Sector. She has more than 10 years experience in different roles from Quality Assurance and Regulatory Affairs through Management and Consulting for the design, development, implementation, verification and validation and clinical evaluation as well as auditing of medical, IVDs and medicinal products. Katerina is a QMS auditor and technical expert in the field of medical devices for two EU Notified Bodies, while she contributes as Consultant to the IVD Prequalification team of WHO.
- Dimitrios Katehakis has led the Center for eHealth Applications and Services (CeHA) at the Institute of Computer Science, FORTH since 2010. His work centers on advancing digital health through innovative EHR services and fostering innovation ecosystems. He has participated in numerous EU co-funded projects, and has collaborated with the University of Maryland Medical School. Since 2011, he has overseen over 400 projects related to operational EHR systems in Greece's National Health System (NHS). Dimitrios has published extensively in international journals and is a regular reviewer and program committee member for leading journals and conferences, including BMC HSR, IJMI, IEEE BHI, JBHI, and MEDINFO.

The ExAB will provide professional guidance on specific topics related to identifying the factors that encourage and/or hinder healthcare innovation. The board will help us steer the project, ensuring its success and societal relevance. Each member has been contacted directly by the project and briefed about our goals and intended impacts; all

have agreed to serve as Advisors, contributing their expertise and also acting as amplifiers, supporting our communication efforts and using their networks to spread the word about EVOLVE2CARE. We have asked the ExAB to commit to holding three sixty-minute online meetings (~M8, M14, M20) and (budget permitting) we will sponsor their participation at our last event to be held in-person. The agenda for the first ExAB meeting is in development and will be discussed at the Plenary meeting to be held in Istanbul May 12 2025.

2nd activity: Ethics Advisory Board and Independent Ethics Advisor

The activities associated with overseeing the projects' Ethics monitoring and reporting are driven by WP6, (see also Section 4.6 below) while the staff effort to cover these is reported in WP5, T5.2. During the reporting period, work was concentrated on the formation and recruitment of members for the Ethics Advisory Board (EAB) and the Independent Ethics Advisor (IEA). The consortium defined the tasks and responsibilities of these roles, and through its academic contacts, extended invitations to experts to apply for the roles of IEA and EAB. EAB members will serve voluntarily, providing opinions on ethical matters at the coordinator's request. The IEA is a paid position responsible for conducting ethics reviews of the open call shortlisted applicants. To support the IEA's work, the necessary template documents for the reviews were developed. Following the successful completion of the invitation process, interviews were held with candidates, resulting in the appointment of Prof. Abdolraspul Habibipour as the IEA, and Prof. George Konstantinidis and Giuseppe Conti as external members of the EAB. Looking ahead, this task will focus on closely monitoring project activities and carrying out the ethics reviews of the open call applications. The WP will submit D6.1 - OEI - Requirement No. 1 on M24, a report on the ethics requirements set by the GA which are the ethics reviews of the open-call applications.

3rd activity: Technical and innovation management

During the reporting period, the methodology for addressing the management of external innovations was developed. It comprises the following steps:

Step 1: Preliminary Evaluation via Application Form

During the application phase, applicants are assessed through Sploro's Platform Application Form. Two targeted questions are included to provide a preliminary evaluation of the innovation's commercialization potential:

1. *"Describe your strategy for the broad implementation of the proposed solution in the HealthTech system."*

2. “Describe the team – their expertise, capabilities, and motivation to advance this innovation. The team should align with the proposed work plan and objectives.”

The responses to those questions will form the foundation for the initial evaluation of each innovation.

Step 2: Innovation Potential Assessment Using Innovation Radar Tool

Once innovators are selected, their commercialization potential will be further assessed using the **Innovation Radar Tool**, which offers a structured framework to identify high-potential innovations and key development areas.

Step 3: Follow-On Interview and KPI Goal Setting

The next phase involves a *follow-on interview* focused on setting goals and defining Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) in three key areas:

- Product validation
- Market validation
- Regulatory compliance

To support this process, materials submitted during the application will be reviewed to verify the **Technological Readiness Level (TRL)** of each applicant.

Step 4: Mid-Term Status Check and Final Residency Interview

Midway through the program, a *Mid-Term Status Check* will be conducted, followed by a *final residency interview*. These sessions aim to review:

- Progress toward initial KPIs
- Accomplishments and milestones
- Challenges and adjustments made during the residency

The **KTH Innovation Readiness Tool**, will be used during the final residency interview to further guide the discussion on the commercialization potential and provide structured feedback to the applicants.

4th activity: IPR in EVOLVE2CARE's external innovations

Management of intellectual property rights (IPR) for external innovations - that is, the Innovations which are developed during the funded residencies - will involve monitoring IP ownership stemming from work conducted during their residency at the Living Labs. To date, the process has been determined as follows: it was decided that, following their selection and matching for a residency, the researchers/innovators and

Living Labs will assess the need for IPR agreements and other documentation on a case by case basis. This has been included in the guidelines for the application process. EVOLVE2CARE representatives will speak with each of the accepted innovators and LLs about any concerns they may have regarding their intellectual property rights, and appropriate measures will be put in place. At the conclusion of the residency period, the final evaluation of each innovation will also take the IPR status into account.

4.5.3. Task 5.3 Quality, Risk, and Data Management Plan

This task is part of D.2 Interim Report (Data Management Plan). It outlines how the project manages the research data it generates, ensuring compliance with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), data protection laws (notably the GDPR), and Horizon Europe’s Open Science policy.

The DMP details the types of data collected, how they are stored, shared, preserved, and what ethical and legal considerations are involved, particularly important given that the project includes vulnerable users and collects personal health data.

The results of the DMP were reached through:

- Initial planning and definition of data workflows in early project phases.
- Consultation with partners responsible for data collection, especially those dealing with pilot activities involving real users.
- Adaptation of the DMP to reflect the specific types of data collected in the early project stages (e.g. user surveys, interviews, health assessments).
- Integration of GDPR-compliant procedures, like informed consent, anonymisation, and secure data storage.
- Application of FAIR principles, including metadata standards, repository choices (e.g. Zenodo), and clear data licensing.
- Ongoing monitoring and updates, acknowledging that the DMP is a “living document” to be revised as the project evolves.

The conclusions reached regarding the first interim report were:

- The project has successfully put in place robust data governance practices ensuring ethical, secure, and FAIR-compliant data handling.
- Special attention has been given to the protection of personal and sensitive data, which is crucial given the nature of the user population.
- The project has committed to open access for research outputs where possible, and data sharing will occur via trusted repositories with proper documentation and licensing.
- The DMP will be updated as needed, especially following pilot implementation and the generation of additional datasets.

4.6. WP6 – Ethics requirements

Work Package 6 is responsible for ensuring that the project is compliant with the ethics requirements set out in the Grant Agreement and the Ethics summary report. Staff effort related to carrying out the Ethics activities is conducted under the auspices of T5.2, as described above (see section 4.5.2). The WP will submit D6.1 - OEI - Requirement No. 1 on M24, a report on the ethics requirements set by the GA which are the ethics reviews of the open-call applications.

5. Project Impact and policy recommendations

As this is the first reporting period of EVOLVE2CARE, the key expected impacts are not yet fully realized. However, important groundwork has been laid to ensure the project's long-term contribution to the HealthTech innovation ecosystem, particularly in the domain of transitional care.

One of the main anticipated impacts of EVOLVE2CARE is to enhance knowledge on effective experimentation frameworks for testing innovations. While the actual experimentation phase among Living Labs (LLs) and innovators is yet to commence, significant preparatory activities have been completed, including the development of Open Call documentation and platforms. Furthermore, the identification of key barriers and facilitators within the HealthTech innovation landscape has yielded early tangible results. These insights, detailed in Deliverable 1.1, will feed into the creation of a consolidated one-pager for policymakers, providing targeted policy recommendations to support innovation uptake that will be included in the interim policy recommendations (M12).

Another important contribution is the development of the KPI Framework, which offers guidance on the critical factors to measure for evidence-based decision-making in transitional care. The KPI Repository is envisioned as a central reference point for HealthTech innovations, helping to foster a shared understanding among stakeholders. By tracking and reporting on these KPIs, innovators can demonstrate that their solutions meet not only technical and regulatory standards but also the real needs of end users. This approach strengthens the validation process, supporting the long-term adoption and success of new technologies in healthcare environments.

Importantly, the Impact Assessment KPI Repository does not focus on individual companies or stakeholders but evaluates the overall HealthTech innovation ecosystem. These KPIs are designed to assess initiatives that contribute to the successful adoption of innovation in transitional care. Policymakers can utilize this framework to ensure that funded or supported innovations are aligned with broader healthcare objectives and are generating sustainable, meaningful impact across the system.

Through these activities, EVOLVE2CARE is building a foundation for impactful innovation, aiming to bridge the gap between technological development and actual healthcare needs, while also providing policymakers with actionable tools and recommendations to support the sustainable advancement of transitional care.

6. Conclusions

The first six months of the EVOLVE2CARE project have been successfully completed, with significant progress made in stakeholder engagement, KPI framework development, and preparations for the upcoming experimentation activities. The foundation laid during this period ensures a smooth transition into the next phase of the project.

The next interim report, scheduled for Month 12 (M12), will primarily focus on Phase 2 and provide detailed updates on the progress of Work Package 2 (WP2), including the launch of the Open Calls and the development of the Accelup marketplace and related services.